

Bioelectrochemically-improved anaerobic digestion of fishery processing industrial wastewater

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ABSTRACT

Anaerobic digestion (AD) is an environmentally friendly technology that can harness bioenergy from fishery processing wastewaters, which are usually treated with thermal and aerobic processes, yielding no coproduct. The integration of anaerobic digestion with a bioelectrochemical system (BES) represents a novel strategy to improve the overall stability, efficiency, and bioenergy recovery of the process. This study aims to evaluate the long-term performance of a 7.5 L AD-BES system treating real fishery processing wastewater as single substrate. It also examines the system's resilience to fluctuations in organic loading rate (OLR), extended periods of electrical and substrate starvation, and the progressive hydraulic disconnection of BES modules. Operated at an OLR of $0.6 \text{ g}_{\text{COD}} \text{ L}^{-1} \text{ day}^{-1}$ and a cell voltage of 0.7 V, the AD-BES demonstrated effective wastewater treatment and biogas production, achieving a chemical oxygen demand (COD) removal efficiency of 85–93% and a methane yield of 200–600 $\text{L}_{\text{CH}_4} \text{ kg}_{\text{COD}}^{-1}$. The system demonstrated resilience against OLR fluctuations, while prolonged electrical starvation periods (120 h and 192 h) did not determine any deterioration of the electrical response of the bioelectrodes. The progressive BES modules disconnection from the main AD reactor affected COD removal efficiency, volatile fatty acids (VFA) concentration in the digestate effluent, and methane content of the produced biogas, with minor impact in biogas production rate and yield. Microbial analysis indicated a high level of shared microbial sequences across the bioelectrodes biofilms and bulk liquid phases, indicating that the microbial community maintained the same functional roles within the different environments.

1. Introduction

In the fish processing industry, up to 50% of the starting raw material gets discarded in form of waste [1,2]. Typically, fishery processing wastewaters are treated with aerobic or thermal processes, which does not yield any valuable coproduct [3–5]. However, they are rich in biodegradable components and could represent a promising substrate for methane production in anaerobic digestion (AD) [6–8].

In the AD process, organic matter is decomposed by a mixed community of anaerobic microorganisms, leading to biogas as final gas product, consisting mostly of CO_2 and CH_4 with some impurities (H_2S , O_2 , N_2 , H_2O), and digestate as liquid effluent rich in micro and macronutrients, that can be used as fertilizer [9,10]. Biogas represents a renewable biofuel and can be used for heating and cogeneration of electricity and heat. Biogas can also be upgraded to biomethane, which can be utilized for direct grid injection, by removing the CO_2 and

impurities and therefore increasing the methane content up to 95–98%.

In a previous study, Eiroa et al. [1] observed methane production yields in the range of 260–350 $\text{L}_{\text{CH}_4} \text{ kg}_{\text{VS}}^{-1}$ (VS, volatile solids), digesting various types of fish waste (tuna, sardine, mackerel and needle fish solid fish waste) in batch AD experiments at a low solid content of 1% total solids (TS). Bückner et al. [8] reported a methane yield of 540 $\text{L}_{\text{CH}_4} \text{ kg}_{\text{VS}}^{-1}$ with thermomechanical processed carp (*Cyprinus carpio*) waste at 29.1% TS and a batch time of 21 days. Choe et al. [5] reported a maximum methane yield of 219 $\text{L}_{\text{CH}_4} \text{ kg}_{\text{VS}}^{-1}$ in an AD plant supplemented with bamboo hydrochar, and operated with melted and homogenized fish solid waste as only substrate at 7% TS. Zappi et al. [6,7] obtained methane yields in the range 121–236 $\text{L}_{\text{CH}_4} \text{ kg}_{\text{COD}}^{-1}$ with different types of fishery (catfish and shrimp) processing wastewaters. All these results demonstrate a high variability in methane yield with this kind of substrates, therefore highlighting the needs for further study of scaled-up systems, operated in industrially-relevant conditions (i.e. continuous

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or semi-continuous operation, fluctuating organic loading rates, starvation periods, etc.)

One strategy that received attention to improve bioenergy recovery from the AD process is its integration with bioelectrochemical systems (BES) [11,12]. BES are a novel technology composed of an electrochemical cell where one or two (bio)electrodes are coated with a biological catalyst composed of electroactive microorganisms (EAM), capable of performing extracellular electron transfer with the solid electrodes. Integrating AD with BES (AD-BES) can offer several synergistic advantages, such as improved start-up performance [13], improved biogas composition (biogas upgrading) [14–17], increased stability towards nitrogen and/or organic acids overloads [18,19], and increased methane production [20]. At the anode of AD-BES, small organic molecules, such as acetate, are oxidized, and the resulting electrons are transported through an external electrical circuit to the cathode (Eq. (1)) [21,22]. At the cathode, these electrons can be used directly by EAM (Eq. (2)) or hydrogen can be produced and used by hydrogenotrophic methanogens to reduce CO₂ to methane, in the so called electromethanogenesis process (Eq. (3), Eq. (4)) [23]. The rate and the occurrence of these reactions depends on the applied cathode potential, expressed against the Standard Hydrogen Electrode (SHE).

Few studies investigated the effect of intermittent energy supply in AD-BES [24,25] and BES [26–28], aimed at validating system operation with intermittent energy sources such as solar energy or grid-energy surplus. However, the effect of prolonged (>100 h) electrical starvation periods in AD-BES operated with realistic process substrates is not as well covered in literature. Zakaria & Dhar [24] reported the effect of OCV (open circuit voltage) cycles of 6 and 12 h each day on a laboratory-scale AD-BES fed with glucose. In OCV the BES modules are disconnected from the power source, resulting in no additional voltage supplied to the system, therefore determining a state of electrical starvation, since in this condition the EAM cannot utilize the anode as electron acceptor for their metabolism [28]. In this study, the OCV cycle of 6 h day⁻¹ did not affect biomethane generation, while keeping the system in OCV for 12 h day⁻¹ resulted in a substantial deterioration of performances [24]. This is in contrast with Zhang et al. [25], who showed that an OCV cycle of 12 h day⁻¹ was the optimal one in terms of methane yield within the 0–24 h day⁻¹ interval. Ruiz et al. [28] proved that electrical and substrate starvation periods shorter than 5 days do not affect BES performance, which could recover fully their electrical response in the subsequent batch cycle.

In conclusion, fishery processing wastewaters represent a promising substrate for anaerobic digestion, despite their high variability in process performances. However, no studies have yet reported the use of these wastewaters as substrate in AD-BES systems. Additionally, long-term studies under semi-continuous conditions and information on system response to prolonged starvation periods are lacking in the literature. This study aims to report and evaluate the inoculation, adaptation and long-term operation of a semi-continuous AD-BES system treating real fishery processing wastewater as single substrate and compare its performances with those of ordinary AD treating fish wastes. Furthermore, the present study examines the AD-BES response to prolonged electrical and substrate starvation periods which may occur in industrial field applications and the impact of sequential BES hydraulic disconnection on the AD process conditions and performances. Finally, post-mortem microbial analysis aims to elucidate the microbial composition and functional roles of the system components (anodes, cathodes, BES electrolyte and AD medium).

2. Materials and methods

2.1. AD-BES system

The AD-BES laboratory plant was constituted by a 5 L jacketed anaerobic digestion tank, externally connected with a stack of five BES modules (0.5 L each one), which were inserted in the AD recirculation loop. This configuration was selected based on the assessment performed by Park et al. [12], where the single-chamber, modular, side-stream AD-BES stood out as a promising approach in terms of industrial scalability. In this configuration, both the bioanodes and the biocathodes are immersed in the AD medium, which is recirculated constantly between the AD reactor and the BES modules [29]. The side-stream approach offers the advantage of easier integration inside the AD system, without the need for direct modification on the main AD reactor. Additionally, it provides operational flexibility since the BES can be controlled, operated, and, if necessary, serviced externally from the AD reactor. Furthermore, using a modular approach would easily allow to tune the number of active modules in the BES stack, in correlation with the AD process necessities.

A scheme of the experimental set-up is reported in Fig. 1-A, while Fig. 1-B shows a schematic of the BES stack and single module. Each BES module in the stack was composed by a poly(methyl methacrylate) (PMMA) frame, where a series of 4 anodes and 4 cathodes (electrically connected in parallel) were inserted. Each electrode had an estimated surface area of 47.5 cm², calculated considering the projected area of the enclosing cylinder. The distance between each anode and cathode was 10 mm. Each BES module was hydraulically separated from the others through a PMMA plate. The modules were operated hydraulically in parallel, and the complete stack was kept together by 2 external stainless steel (SS) plates.

Carbon fiber brushes with an internal titanium current collector (MillRose, USA), presenting a diameter of 19 mm and a length of 70 mm, were used as anodes. 3D-printed SS electrodes, manufactured via selective laser melting technique (RenAM500Q, Renishaw Iberica, Spain) were utilized as cathodes. Stainless steel 17-4PH, a kind of martensitic stainless steel, was used as printing material. Each electrode was constituted (visually) by a cylinder of 19 mm diameter and 70 mm height, with a gyroid-kind internal structure. This type of geometry was aimed at maximizing the surface/volume ratio of the cathodes. Photos of anodes, cathodes and BES modules are provided in Supplementary Information. An Ag/AgCl reference electrode (+0.195 V vs SHE, Xi'an Yima Opto-electrical Technology, China) was placed between the anode and the cathode lines of each BES module. The electrical connection to the external circuit was made using stainless steel frames as current collectors. The complete BES stack was electrically connected in parallel and controlled at a constant voltage using a power source (TENMA 72–2715, Farnell, Spain).

The recirculation rate from the AD reactor to the individual BES modules was fixed at 100 mL min⁻¹ using two multichannel peristaltic pumps (HF-Lab, Hygiaflex, Spain). The AD tank was kept in mixed conditions using a stirring plate. The temperature was kept constant at 35°C with a thermostatic bath connected to the external jacket (Huber thermostat CC-K6, Huber, Germany). An off-gas tube was connected to the head space of the AD reactor for biogas collection and measurement of its production rate. The tube was connected through a condensation trap to a gas-meter (MilliGasCounter MGC-1, Ritter, Germany) and from there to a Tedlar bag of 5 L.

The AD-BES plant was operated in a step-batch mode, by partially discharging 2.5 L of treated wastewater and feeding an equal amount of fresh substrate every 3–4 days. Consequently, each batch period had a duration of 3–4 days. A N₂-buffer Tedlar bag was connected to the AD reactor head-space during the operations of discharge/refilling, to maintain the anaerobic conditions and avoid atmospheric air intrusion. The hydraulic retention time (HRT) of the plant was kept between 9 and 12 days during the experimental campaign.

Fig. 1. A) scheme of the AD-BES laboratory plant. FI = flow indicator, CI = current indicator. The current was calculated based on Ohm's law from the (V_1-V_2) voltage drop in the circuit resistance. B-a) assembled BES stack. B-b) explosion scheme of the BES stack. B-c) explosion scheme of a single BES module.

The magnetic stirrer under the AD reactor was switched off 30 min before discharging the wastewater to allow the solids and biomass to settle. As a result, only the supernatant was discharged, leading to an accumulation of solids inside the reactor. The solid retention time (SRT) was calculated following Eq. (5), where C_d is the solids concentration in the reactor, and C_{out} is the solids concentration in the effluent.

$$SRT = HRT \cdot \frac{C_d}{C_{out}} \quad (5)$$

The estimated SRT was between 10 and 25 days. This range was determined by assuming either total solid retention, resulting in a C_d concentration equal to that of the influent (10.5 g L^{-1}), or no retention, resulting in a C_d concentration equal to that of the effluent (4.4 g L^{-1}).

2.2. Media composition

A synthetic, acetate-based mineral medium was adopted as feeding solution during inoculation and start-up of the AD-BES plant. The mineral medium was composed of 450 mg L^{-1} NaCl, 165 mg L^{-1} $\text{MgCl}_2 \cdot 6 \text{ H}_2\text{O}$, 13.6 mg L^{-1} CaCl_2 , 15.3 mg L^{-1} Mg_2SO_4 , 8.4 g L^{-1} NaHCO_3 , 2.5 g L^{-1} CH_3COONa , 128 mg L^{-1} K_2HPO_4 , 50 mg L^{-1} NH_4Cl , 1 mL L^{-1} trace elements solution and 5 mL L^{-1} vitamins solution [30]. Wastewaters 1 and 2 were two different batches of shrimp processing industrial wastewater, collected from a local company. Prior to use, both wastewaters were diluted with tap water, in order to adjust the TS in the 1% range, reported as the optimal for biogas production from fish waste [31]. Wastewater 1 was diluted in 1:3 ratio of (1 part wastewater, 3 parts tap water) while Wastewater 2 was diluted with a ratio of 1:4. The physiochemical characteristics of the acetate medium and the fishery processing wastewaters are reported in Table S1.

2.3. Monitoring protocol and data analysis

The treated wastewater was sampled from the AD reactor effluent, at the end of each performed batch cycle. The samples were analyzed in terms of pH and conductivity, using a HQ40 multimeter (Hach, Spain). Cuvette tests were utilized for the analysis of chemical oxygen demand (COD), both total and soluble parts (LCK 014 kits, Hach, Spain), total ammoniacal nitrogen (TAN) (LCK 302 kits, Hach, Spain) and alkalinity (LCK 362 kits, Hach, Spain). The volatile fatty acids (VFA) content was determined based on the Nordmann method (AT100 Lab Titrator, Hach, Spain). The biogas produced by the AD-BES plant was stored in a Tedlar bag. Its daily production rate was calculated through the installed gas meter. The biogas composition was measured using a gas chromatograph (490 Micro GC Natural Gas Analyzer, Agilent, Spain) equipped with a dual channel cabinet and a thermal conductivity detector. Channel 1, which used argon as the carrier gas, was equipped with a 10-

meter CP-Molsieve 5A column and was used for separating and analyzing the permanent gases H_2 , O_2 , N_2 , and CH_4 . Channel 2, which used helium as the carrier gas, contained a CP-PoraPlot U column and was used to separate hydrogen sulfide (H_2S) and CO_2 .

The methane yield was estimated by the ratio between produced methane and added organic matter (COD), for each batch cycle. The organic matter removal efficiency (η_{COD}) was calculated by Eq. (6), where COD_{IN} and COD_{OUT} refer to the COD concentration of the influent and effluent wastewater, respectively fed and discharged during a batch cycle.

$$\eta_{\text{COD}}(\%) = \frac{\text{COD}_{\text{IN}} - \text{COD}_{\text{OUT}}}{\text{COD}_{\text{IN}}} \cdot 100 \quad (6)$$

The current of each BES module was calculated through Ohm's law by measuring the voltage drop across a 5.3Ω shunt resistance, recorded using a multichannel data acquisition (DAQ) board (PicoLog 1216, Farnell, Spain). The current densities were calculated considering the geometrical surface of the electrodes for the current normalization. The potentials of anode and cathode were punctually measured during BES tests, with a portable multimeter. The average batch daily coulombs exchanged (expressed in C day^{-1}) were calculated as reported in Eq. (7), where I is the current flown in the system for each batch cycle, t_0 and t_f are respectively the starting and final time of each batch cycle, and n is the total duration of the cycle, expressed in days.

$$\text{C Day}^{-1} = \int_{t_0}^{t_f} I dt / n \quad (7)$$

The electromethanation coefficient was calculated as the ratio between the electrical charge transferred through BES electrical circuit and the total charge stored within produced CH_4 [32].

2.4. Experimental operation of the AD-BES

Table 1 reports the operational conditions of the AD-BES, which was operated for >5 months with wastewater as only substrate feed. The total experimental time of the plant, considering inoculation, adaptation, and operation phases, has been >8 months. The key variable determining each phase of the experiment was the substrate provided to the plant. During the inoculation phase, only an acetate medium was used. In the adaptation phase, the substrate consisted of an acetate medium mixed with progressively increasing concentrations of real fishery processing wastewater. In the operation phase, the plant was fed exclusively with wastewater.

The adopted inoculum mixture for the inoculation of the AD-BES plant was composed of 25% anaerobic digestion sludge from the local wastewater treatment plant, 50% acetate-based medium (detailed in Section 2.2) and 25% effluent from a laboratory-scale microbial fuel cell

Table 1
Experimental operational procedure of the AD-BES plant.

Phase	Batch (3–4 days duration)	Substrate feed	Voltage (V)	Active BES modules
Inoculation	1–3	Acetate medium	0.3	5
	4–6		0.5	
	7–10		0.7	
Adaptation	11–12	75% acetate medium +25% wastewater 1	0.7	5
	13–14	50% acetate medium +50% wastewater 1		
	15–16	25% acetate medium +75% wastewater 1		
Operation	17–20	100% Wastewater 1	0.7	5
Open circuit voltage (OCV)	21–22	100% Wastewater 1	OCV	5
Operation	23–25	100% Wastewater 1	0.7	5
Shut down test	26	100% Wastewater 1	OCV	5
Operation	27–34	100% Wastewater 1	0.7	5
Operation	35–44	100% Wastewater 2	0.7	5
				4
Progressive BES modules disconnection	45–46	100% Wastewater 2	0.7	3
	47–48			2
	49–50			1
	51–52			0
Operation	53–54	100% Wastewater 2	0.7	5
	55–64			

(MFC) [33]. The BES reactors were polarized at a progressively increasing cell voltage from 0.3 to 0.7 V. The operation voltage of 0.7 V was chosen based on previous literature results [34–37]. For instance, between the five different voltages (0V, 0.3V, 0.7V, 1.2V and 1.8V) tested by Zhang et al. [37] in single-chambered AD-BES systems, 0.7 V provided the highest methane yield compared to an AD control. The AD-BES was gradually acclimated during six batch cycles to the real wastewater feed. The plant was operated at an OLR of $0.8\text{--}1 \text{ kg}_{\text{COD}} \text{ m}^{-3} \text{ d}^{-1}$ from batch 17 onwards. This low OLR was selected based on Park et al. [38] who reported better process performance for lower OLR, achieving an higher COD removal efficiency (up to 95%) and methane yield (up to $610 \text{ L}_{\text{CH}_4} \text{ kg}_{\text{VS}}^{-1} \text{ d}^{-1}$) for decreasing the OLR from 3.64 to $1.95 \text{ kg}_{\text{VS}} \text{ m}^{-3} \text{ day}^{-1}$ in the anaerobic mono-digestion of dead fish wastewater [38].

A benchmark trial with the BES stack operated in OCV was performed during batch 21–22 to evaluate the contribution of electro-active microbes in degrading the organic matter content of wastewater, and consequences in terms of biogas quality and production rate. During batch 26, a shutdown test was performed on the AD-BES, to determine the residual amount of CH_4 that would be produced in such a scenario. This test started with a recently fed plant, switching off the thermostatic bath, the power source, and the magnetic stirrer, while keeping the recirculation flux (from AD to BES modules) activated. The test lasted 5 days, until the biogas production stopped. From cycle 35, the feeding substrate was switched from the first to the second batch of wastewater.

During batches 47–54 the BES modules were progressively hydraulically disconnected from the AD-BES. Following this procedure, it was possible to investigate the effect of the number of active BES modules on the process outputs and performances. The disconnected BES were kept polarized at 0.7 V and fed with wastewater, to prevent the microbial community from being inhibited by the lack of polarization of the electrodes or substrate availability. The plant was then operated again with all the BES modules from batches 55 to 64.

2.5. Microbial community characterization

At the end of the experiment, the AD-BES system was disassembled and samples from the anode biofilm, cathode biofilm, AD tank liquid phase, and electrolyte liquid phase inside the BES reactors were collected. The samples from the electrode's biofilms were taken from a casual anode and cathode for each of the 5 BES modules. Results of microbial characterization of homologous samples (5 anodes, 5 cathodes, 5 electrolyte samples) were treated like replicates. These samples underwent microbial DNA extraction utilizing the ZymoBIOMICS DNA Miniprep Kit (Zymo Research) in adherence to the manufacturer's guidelines, with DNA purity and concentration determined via a Qubit 4.0 Fluorometer (Thermo Fisher Scientific). The V3-V4 hypervariable region of the 16S rRNA gene was then amplified using the primers S-D-Bact-0341-b-s-17 (5'-CCTACGGGNGGCWGCAG-3') and the S-D-Bact-0785-a-A-21 (5'-GACTACHVGGGTATCTAATCC-3'), followed by validation of successful amplification through gel electrophoresis. Amplicons were then purified using the AMPure XP system (Beckman Coulter, Beverly, USA) to remove unwanted sequences and primer dimers. Indexed adapters were attached to the amplicons in preparation for the Illumina sequencing using the Nextera XT Index Kit (Illumina, San Diego, USA). Libraries were then quantified using the Qubit 4.0 Fluorometer (Thermo Fisher Scientific), ensuring optimal quality and quantity. These libraries were pooled in equimolar ratios and paired-end sequenced (2×300) on an Illumina MiSeq platform.

The resulting raw sequence data underwent preprocessing using QIIME2 [39]. Initial steps included demultiplexing and quality filtering to remove low-quality reads, followed by denoising with DADA2, enabling the pinpointing of amplicon sequence variants (ASVs) with high precision [40]. Taxonomy was assigned to these ASVs by aligning them against the SILVA reference database [41]. Subsequent diversity analyses were performed. For more detailed statistical analyses, the processed data were transferred into the R computing environment [42]. Within R, the "phylose" package was employed to manage the microbiome data, including ordination and visualization at the order and phylum levels. The "microeco" package was specifically utilized to generate representations of microbial compositions and relative abundances. Functional annotation of the microbial communities was accomplished using the FAPROTAX database, which facilitated the prediction of potential metabolic functions based on the identified taxonomic profiles. The results were then visualized through heatmaps to display the distribution of predicted functions across the different samples, providing a comparative view of functional capacities [43]. Comparisons of ASVs shared between the different environments were visualized using Venn diagrams, allowing for a clear depiction of unique and shared microbial taxa.

3. Results and discussions

3.1. System chemical parameters

During the inoculation phase, which lasted 10 batches, the AD-BES was fed with acetate medium, while progressively higher cell voltages (ranging from 0.3 to 0.7 V) were applied to acclimate the microbial community to the electrodes. The average OLR during this phase was $0.14 \pm 0.03 \text{ g}_{\text{COD}} \text{ L}_{\text{reactor}}^{-1} \text{ day}^{-1}$, as depicted in Fig. 2-a.

Subsequently in the adaptation phase, the system was progressively fed with an increasing amount of real wastewater, up to 100%. During the operation phase, spanning from batch 16 till 66, only shrimp processing industrial wastewater was supplied to the AD-BES, at an OLR of $0.85 \pm 0.22 \text{ g}_{\text{COD}} \text{ L}_{\text{reactor}}^{-1} \text{ day}^{-1}$, fluctuating daily due to varying wastewater quantities. Fig. 2-b illustrates the COD removal efficiency, which displayed an upward trend during the inoculation phase, stabilizing at approximately 80% efficiency during the adaptation phase. Subsequently, the COD removal efficiency stabilized at $89 \pm 4\%$, resulting in a discharged effluent COD of around 1 g L^{-1} throughout the

Fig. 2. a) OLR trend during the experiment. b) COD removal efficiency. The line connecting the points and the vertical dashed lines serves only to guide the eye. The colored line on top of each graph visually indicates each experimental phase reported in the legend.

entire operational period. For the entire experimental time, the effluent pH remained stable around 7.8 ± 0.2 without any significant deviation, indicating a high buffer capacity of the system that mitigated overacidification risks associated with fluctuating OLRs. The effluent conductivity remained constant at 11 ± 2 mS cm⁻¹ throughout the operational phase.

As reported in Fig. 3-a and Fig. 3-b, from the start of the experimentation VFA and TAN showed a decreasing trend, and both reached values near zero towards the end of the inoculation period. However, during the adaptation phase, VFA and TAN concentrations increased, reaching a final VFA level around 1000 mg L⁻¹ and a TAN of 347 mg L⁻¹. The VFA concentration showed a decreasing trend during the first operation phase, decreasing from 1333 mg L⁻¹ at batch 19 to 573 mg L⁻¹ at batch 37, stabilizing around that value until the beginning of the BES disconnection test. The disconnection of the second BES module determined a decrease of the VFA concentration to 373 mg L⁻¹, while the subsequent disconnection of the fourth module caused a sudden VFA accumulation, up to 662 mg L⁻¹ after the fifth module was disconnected.

A decreasing trend of the VFA level can be observed after the reconnection of the five BES modules, which stabilized at around 390–400 mg L⁻¹, lower than before the BES disconnection trial.

TAN concentrations increased from 475 mg L⁻¹ to around 750–800 mg L⁻¹ during operation phase. At a pH of 7.8, these TAN values led to a free ammonia concentration of roughly 25–27 mg L⁻¹, which is far below the inhibiting value of 0.5 g L⁻¹ [44]. These values were stable for the rest of the experiment. As shown in Fig. 3-c, the alkalinity level was between 5 and 6 g L⁻¹ during inoculation phase, therefore when using the acetate medium as electrolyte. The progressive introduction of wastewater determined a stabilization of the alkalinity level to around 3.4 g L⁻¹.

3.2. Methane production and yield

Fig. 4 reports the average biogas production rate, normalized by the batch duration in days and the reactor volume (Fig. 4-a), the trend of the methane yield (Fig. 4-b), and the measured methane content (%) of the

Fig. 3. Concentrations in anaerobic digester digestate of: a) volatile fatty acids, b) TAN, c) alkalinity. The line connecting the points and the vertical dashed lines serves only to guide the eye. The colored line on top of each graph indicates visually each experimental phase reported in the legend.

Fig. 4. a) average biogas production rate for each batch. b) methane yield. c) methane content in the biogas. The line connecting the points and the vertical dashed lines serves only to guide the eye. The colored line on top of each graph indicates visually each experimental phase reported in the legend.

biogas (Fig. 4-c).

During the inoculation phase, biogas production remained below $150 \text{ L}_{\text{biogas}} \text{ m}_{\text{reactor}}^{-3} \text{ day}^{-1}$, as illustrated in Fig. 4-a. This low production was attributed to the insufficient OLR, which did not provide enough substrate to sustain a higher biogas production. The methane yield was estimated around $400 \text{ L}_{\text{CH}_4} \text{ kg}_{\text{COD}}^{-1}$, as shown in Fig. 4-b. This was higher than the theoretical yield of methanogenesis of $350 \text{ L}_{\text{CH}_4} \text{ kg}_{\text{COD}}^{-1}$ [45], due to the accumulation of solids in the reactor, achieved by allowing solids to settle before each batch feeding event.

Throughout the adaptation phase, biogas production followed the OLR increasing trend similarly to VFA and TAN, reaching a maximum of $731 \text{ L}_{\text{biogas}} \text{ m}_{\text{reactor}}^{-3} \text{ day}^{-1}$ on batch 21. During the first part of the operation phase (up to batch 45) the biogas production was inconsistent, ranging from 350 to $850 \text{ L}_{\text{biogas}} \text{ m}_{\text{reactor}}^{-3} \text{ day}^{-1}$, with a mean of $582 \pm 120 \text{ L}_{\text{biogas}} \text{ m}_{\text{reactor}}^{-3} \text{ day}^{-1}$. This biogas production corresponded to a methane yield in the range of $300\text{--}600 \text{ L}_{\text{CH}_4} \text{ kg}_{\text{COD}}^{-1}$, with a mean of $450 \pm 69 \text{ L}_{\text{CH}_4} \text{ kg}_{\text{COD}}^{-1}$, in line with values reported in literature [1,5–7]. The BES hydraulic disconnection determined a decrease in biogas production and methane yield, compared to the precedent values, which was not recovered with the reconnection of the BES stack. In fact, from batch 45 to 54, the mean biogas production was $445 \pm 55 \text{ L}_{\text{biogas}} \text{ m}_{\text{reactor}}^{-3} \text{ day}^{-1}$, corresponding to a methane yield of $321 \pm 28 \text{ L}_{\text{CH}_4} \text{ kg}_{\text{COD}}^{-1}$, while from batch 54 onwards the mean biogas production and methane yield were respectively $444 \pm 96 \text{ L}_{\text{biogas}} \text{ m}_{\text{reactor}}^{-3} \text{ day}^{-1}$ and $316 \pm 31 \text{ L}_{\text{CH}_4} \text{ kg}_{\text{COD}}^{-1}$.

The biogas was mainly composed of CH_4 and CO_2 , with minor contributions of N_2 and O_2 , likely due to contamination of external air, while H_2S was detected always in amounts below 1%. The O_2 content never exceeded 3.5% while N_2 was present at $8 \pm 5\%$ and CO_2 represented the $20 \pm 6\%$ of the gas composition. H_2 was never detected in the effluent biogas (0%). The absence of unreacted hydrogen indicates that 100% of the electron output of the BES stack was consumed within the

AD process. The methane content in the biogas presented an overall increasing trend during inoculation and adaptation phases, as reported in Fig. 4-c. During the first part of the operation phase, the biogas' methane content was inconsistent, ranging from 58% to 75%, to then stabilize at 68% from batch 38. The BES modules disconnection determined a sudden drop in methane content, which reached the minimum of 54%. After the BES module reconnection, the methane content increased again to 65–66% within the subsequent batches.

3.3. Electrical performances

Fig. 5 presents the electrical response and average batch daily coulombs exchanged for the bioelectrodes during the experimental run. As shown in Fig. 5-a, the current density exhibited an increasing trend from the start of the experiment, peaking at 0.9 A m^{-2} by the conclusion of the adaptation phase. However, the current showed a declining trend throughout the operational phase, decreasing from 0.8 A m^{-2} at batch 17 to 0.34 A m^{-2} at batch 43. Correspondingly, the coulomb exchanged followed the trend observed in the VFA concentration, as presented in Fig. 5-b. This correlation can be attributed to the preference of electroactive microorganisms for acetate and other small organic molecules as substrates [46,47]. The anode potentials remained stable at $-389 \pm 88 \text{ mV}$, and the cathode potentials stayed around $-1016 \pm 85 \text{ mV}$, as reported in Fig. S4, resulting in a cell voltage of 0.7 V . The progressive hydraulic disconnection of cell modules did not influence the current density achieved by the remaining BES modules connected to the system. The electromethanation coefficient during operation was $5 \pm 1\%$, meaning that only 5% of the CH_4 was produced by the BES stack when the AD-BES plant was operated with real wastewater, while the remaining 95% of methane was produced by the AD process.

Fig. 5. a) electrical response of the bioelectrodes during the experimental run. b) average daily coulombs exchanged by the bioelectrodes for each batch. The colored line on top of each graph indicates visually each experimental phase reported in the legend.

3.4. Microbial composition analysis

The analysis of the microbial composition within the electrodes, the media of each BES module and the AD tank revealed closely related community structures between the anodes and cathodes, with subtle differences in the abundance of key microbial orders. Fig. 6 illustrates that both the anode and cathode environments harbored a similar spectrum of microbial orders, suggesting that these electrochemically active interfaces shared a common pool of microbial diversity. Most of the exoelectrogens isolated from natural environments belong to the phyla Proteobacteria and Firmicutes, both present in major amount (%) in all environments. These are mostly facultative anaerobic microorganisms which can harvest energy to sustain growth via anaerobic

respiration and fermentation metabolism [48]. Furthermore, certain orders such as Methanosarcinales and Anaerolineales were notably more abundant in the cathode and anode compared to medium and tank environment, and therefore keener to form biofilms on the electrode's surfaces. On the other hand, orders such as Clostridiales and Pseudomonadales were more abundant in the AD tank and BES modules medium, than on the electrodes, and therefore contributing to the overall process from the planktonic phase. In-depth examination of these electroactive genera on the electrodes reveals their crucial roles in the bioelectrochemical processes. Methanosarcinales, a pivotal order within these systems, can perform both acetoclastic and hydrogenotrophic methanogenesis, utilizing either acetate or hydrogen and CO₂ as substrates [49,50]. When present at the anode, this order can utilize acetate

Fig. 6. This figure provides a visual representation of the microbial diversity observed in each of the sampled environments of the BES. Across four environmental samples: anode, cathode, medium, and tank. A) stacked bar chart detailing the relative abundance of different microbial genera within each sample, with a color-coded legend for order identification. B) Pie charts that show the distribution of microbial phyla. The category labeled 'Others' groups the less prevalent phyla.

to produce methane, competing with the electroactive microorganisms for the same substrate and potentially diverting electrons away from electricity generation. On the other hand, when associated to the cathode, this order can utilize the produced hydrogen to reduce CO₂ to methane [51,52]. Additionally, it could utilize the acetate present in bulk to produce methane and CO₂, possibly in a syntrophic network where the locally produced CO₂ gets utilized by the same order, together with the locally produced hydrogen to perform hydrogenotrophic methanogenesis. Anaerolineales, which were also more abundant on the electrodes compared to the liquid sample, are fermenters that can utilize different substrates, such as sugars, peptides, and organic acids, in the AD process. Interestingly, organisms of these order are reported to be able to establish syntrophic interaction with methanogens [53]. Similar findings were reported by Flores-Rodriguez et al. [54], who observed similar syntrophic growths of methanogens on the cathode, enhancing the methanogenic process, and on the anode, together with exoelectrogens.

In the electrodes, although in lesser amounts, other orders with bioelectrochemical capabilities associated with methanogenesis have also been detected. These orders include Geobacterales, Desulfovibrionales, Pseudomonadales, and Clostridiales. *Geobacter* species, which belong to the order Geobacterales, are renowned for their capability to transfer electrons directly to electrodes [55]. These bacteria can form conductive biofilms that enhance electron flow from microbial metabolism to the anode, significantly improving the efficiency of

bioelectrochemical systems [56].

Desulfovibrio species of the order Desulfovibrionales are sulfate-reducing bacteria that contribute to electron transfer processes, aiding in current generation in MFCs. They are particularly effective in anaerobic environments where sulfate is available as an electron acceptor [57].

Pseudomonas species, particularly those within the Pseudomonadales order, are capable of forming biofilms and participating in electron transfer, enhancing the efficiency of MFCs through their metabolic activities. *Pseudomonas putida*, for example, has been identified as an emerging exoelectrogen due to its ability to transfer electrons to electrodes, contributing significantly to electricity generation and bioremediation processes in BES. Studies have shown that *Pseudomonas* species can produce phenazine compounds, which facilitate extracellular electron transfer and enhance the overall electrochemical performance of BES [58,59].

Clostridium species from the order Clostridiales are fermentative bacteria that can also participate in electron transfer under anaerobic conditions, playing a role in bioelectrochemical systems. They are known for their ability to degrade complex organic substrates into simpler compounds, which can then be utilized by other electroactive bacteria in the community. *Clostridium* species have been studied for their potential in enhancing the efficiency of BES through their metabolic activities that produce hydrogen, which can be used as an electron donor [60,61].

Fig. 7. Overview of Microbial ASVs and Predicted Functional Profiles A) The Venn diagram in the upper panel displays the unique and shared Amplicon Sequence Variants (ASVs) among the anode, cathode, medium, and tank environments. Each number within the intersecting and non-intersecting areas represents the count of ASVs, with the corresponding percentage of the total ASVs in parentheses. B) The heatmap represents the distribution of predicted microbial functions based on FAPROTAX analysis across the same four environmental samples. Each row corresponds to a specific metabolic or biogeochemical process, categorized under energy source, carbon cycle (C-cycle), nitrogen cycle (N-cycle), and sulfur cycle (S-cycle), with additional functions grouped under 'Others'. The color gradient indicates the percentage of the community predicted to carry out each function, providing a visual summary of functional potential within each sample.

Despite the observed differences in relative abundances among the various conditions, the analysis of Amplicon Sequence Variants (ASVs) indicated a high level of shared microbial sequences across all four environments, as depicted in the Venn diagram of Fig. 7. This suggests that while the microbial populations adjusted in abundance, the core constituents of the community in terms of ASVs remained consistent. This is in line with the results reported by Lee et al. [62]. The authors compared the microbial communities from the bulk sludge between an AD and an AD-BES. The results showed significant changes in the archaea communities, while the dominant bacterial communities remained unchanged [62]. In the AD-BES, the *Methanosarcina* genus (acetotrophic methanogens, including *Methanosarcina thermophila* and *Methanobacterium formicicum* species) was dominant. Additionally, the overall bacterial population in the AD-BES increased by 40%, leading to an accelerated removal of organic compounds and conversion of volatile fatty acids [62], in line with the results obtained in the present study.

The heatmap of predicted metabolic functions reinforced this observation, showing that potential functional roles were maintained across the anode, cathode, medium, and tank environments. This underlying functional redundancy may contribute to the resilience and stability of the BES. Within this functional framework, certain metabolic pathways emerged as particularly prevalent. The heatmap highlights a significant representation of processes such as anaerobic chemoheterotrophy, fermentation, sulfate respiration and methanogenesis across all conditions, indicating their central role in the system's metabolism. It is interesting to notice how aerobic chemoheterotrophy was more abundant at the cathodes and in the BES modules medium than at the anodes and in the AD tank. Aerobic and anaerobic chemoheterotrophy pathways can co-exist in the same environment, and the presence of low amount of oxygen has beneficial effects on the performance of the AD process, such as higher hydrolysis rate and improved sulfur compounds removal [63,64]. The hydrogen oxidation metabolic pathway was also present in the cathodic region at a higher percentage than the other regions. It could be therefore hypothesized that oxygen-consuming microbes colonized the cathode and utilized the provided hydrogen to reduce oxygen. This effect, even though it diverts electrons from the methane production, can be seen as a syntrophic effect, since it prevents local oxygen presence to be inhibitory against strictly-anaerobic microbes, such as methanogens, therefore maintaining a local anaerobic environment at the cathodes.

3.5. Overall process performances and system response to perturbations

From the overall results of the operation phases, it is possible to observe that the AD-BES plant could successfully operate for >5 months, achieving a stable COD removal of 83–95% while obtaining a high methane yield in the range of 200–600 $L_{CH_4} kg_{COD}^{-1}$. For comparison, Zappi et al. [7] reported a COD removal of 70% with a methane yield of roughly 200 $L_{CH_4} kg_{COD}^{-1}$ for an anaerobic digester digesting shrimp processing wastewaters. Zappi et al. [6] also showed that anaerobic digestion of nutrient-supplemented catfish processing wastewater could achieved a methane yield of 121–236 $L_{CH_4} kg_{COD}^{-1}$.

During batch 21 and 22 (corresponding to a total time of 8 days) the BES stack was operated in OCV to evaluate the impact of the polarized BES stack on the organic loading degradation and the effects of prolonged electrical starvation on the bioelectrodes. No significant effect on COD removal was observed, which remained near 85% for both batches. In batch 22, a decrease in methane yield and production, and VFA concentration was observed, likely due to the lower OLR on that batch rather than the OCV test. At batch 26 a shut-down test was conducted to determine the residual biogas production capacity of the plant, and the effect of prolonged electrical and substrate starvation on the system. This test started with a recently fed plant, switching off the thermostatic bath, the power source, and the magnetic stirrer, while keeping the recirculation flux activated. The test lasted 5 days, resulting in the residual production of 700 $L_{biogas} m_{reactor}^{-3}$, with a complete stop of biogas

production achieved in 90 h. The shutdown did not significantly affect pH, TAN, VFA concentrations or COD removal efficiency after reestablishing ordinary process conditions. From the trend of the electrical performances of the BES stack reported in Fig. 5, it is possible to notice how prolonged starvation periods of 5 days (120 h, electrical and substrate starvation) and 8 days (192 h, electrical starvation) did not result in any deterioration of the bioelectrodes performances. These achieved an average batch current density between 0.69 and 0.85 $A m^{-2}$ in the four batches before the OCV tests (batch 21 and 22) and of 0.73–0.74 $A m^{-2}$ in the 3 batches after the OCV tests, which increased to 0.91 $A m^{-2}$ in the batch after the shut-down test. These results demonstrated the system resiliency during extended periods of starvation, underlining the potential for implementing this technology in real industrial applications characterized possible stops in production. For instance, the fish processing industry is characterized by periods when production stops due to the lack of fish, for example during the winter season. This determines an unavailability of wastewaters and other substrates for the AD-BES, and/or a reduced demand for biogas.

To evaluate the effect of the progressive disconnection of the BES modules from the system, one BES module was disconnected every two batches from batch 45 to 54 (for a total of 35 days), ultimately leaving no BES modules connected to the AD reactor, with only the AD process ongoing. After batch 54, the system was operated with all the five BES modules active up to batch 66, to evaluate the stack recovery time after being progressively switched off. During the progressive BES modules disconnection, the current decreased down to zero (only AD). Reactivating all the modules determined a sharp increase in current to 30 mA (0.32 $A m^{-2}$), which was comparable to the current achieved prior to the disconnection test, but lower than the level obtained during the first operation phase. During the progressive disconnection, COD removal remained stable at 88% during the progressive disconnection of the first three BES modules. However, after disconnecting the 4th and 5th modules, the COD removal dropped to 83%. After reconnecting the entire BES stack, the COD removal raised up to 93%, the highest value of the entire experimentation.

By comparing Fig. 5 with Fig. 2-b, it is evident that after the entire BES stack was reconnected, both current density and coulombs exchanged did not return to the high values observed in the first operation phase. However, the COD removal efficiency did return to its high levels prior to the disconnection test. A possible explanation could be that the electrodes provided a large supporting medium for attached biomass. In comparison to a suspended growth system, attached growth is known to sustain more biomass inside the AD reactor, thus providing greater biological stability and efficiency of COD removal [65]. In most studies, AD-BES are compared to ordinary AD reactors without electrodes. However, only a few studies, including this one, compare AD-BES systems with and without applied voltage. When dealing with complex substrates, it has been reported that the addition of electrodes (which provide a conductive, biocompatible surface) enhances biogas production more significantly than the voltage applied across them [66–68]. This does not imply that applying voltage has no effect, but rather that the benefit of adding a conductive surface may overshadow the effect of the applied voltage.

Based on the results of the BES disconnection tests, it is evident that the BES modules influenced COD removal efficiency, alkalinity, VFA levels, biogas production rate and purity, and methane yield. However, these parameters responded differently to the BES disconnection. The impact on COD removal efficiency and alkalinity became noticeable only after the fifth module was disconnected, with a swift recovery to previous levels once the entire stack was reconnected. VFA levels initially decreased following the disconnection of the second module but began to accumulate when the fourth and fifth modules were disconnected. After the entire stack was reconnected, VFA levels dropped to values lower than those before the disconnection test. Biogas production and methane yield decreased immediately after the first module was disconnected, stabilizing at lower values than before the test, without

recovering even after the entire stack was reconnected. Further disconnections did not significantly affect this trend. The methane content in the biogas decreased after the second module was disconnected, but it began to recover immediately, eventually stabilizing at values lower than those before the test after the stack was reconnected. By comparing the results from the starvation periods with the BES disconnection test, it is evident that shorter-term perturbations (5 and 8 days) did not significantly affect the system. In contrast, prolonged perturbations (35 days) caused substantial changes, with some parameters (biogas production, methane yield, coulombs exchanged/current density, and VFA levels) failing to recover to their original values.

4. Conclusions

In conclusion, an AD-BES was operated for >5 months with shrimp processing industrial wastewater as only substrate, achieving a high and stable chemical oxygen demand removal efficiency of 85–93%, with a high methane yield between 200 and 600 L_{CH₄} kg_{COD}⁻¹. The bioelectrodes could achieve a stable current density of 0.2 A m⁻² after 240 days of operation. These results demonstrate that bioelectrochemically-improved anaerobic digestion is a promising technology for treating fishery processing wastewater, enabling the recovery of bioenergy in the form of methane. Although a limitation of this work is that some operational phases were shorter than the value defining a quasi-steady state (three hydraulic retention times), the system proved to be resilient against OLR fluctuations and prolonged starvation periods. Microbial analysis revealed closely related community structures and functional metabolic role redundancy between the system components, which may contribute to the resilience and stability of the system. The progressive BES modules disconnection affected in different ways the COD removal efficiency, VFA and alkalinity levels in the system, and biogas production and quality. The lack of performance decrease during starvation tests indicated high system stability, suggesting its potential for continuous operation in industrial settings.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Simone Colantoni: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Daniele Molognoni:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Supervision, Project administration, Methodology, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Pablo Sánchez-Cueto:** Writing – review & editing, Investigation. **Charbell De Soto:** Writing – review & editing, Resources. **Pau Bosch-Jimenez:** Writing – review & editing, Funding acquisition. **Radu Ghemis:** Writing – review & editing, Visualization, Supervision, Formal analysis, Data curation. **Eduard Borràs:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Resources, Project administration, Funding acquisition.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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